
**A NEW SUBSPECIES OF *PHYTOECIA (MUSARIA)*
PUNCTICOLLIS (FALDERMANN, 1837) FROM JORDAN
(COLEOPTERA, CERAMBYCIDAE)**

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ABSTRACT: *Phytoecia (Musaria) puncticollis vladyslavi* ssp. n. was described from Jordan on the base of a single totally black male with short antennae and separated upper and lower eye lobes.

KEY WORDS: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Lamiinae, Phytoeciini, taxonomy, new subspecies, Jordan

Phytoecia (Musaria) puncticollis (Faldermann, 1837) was described without exact definition of the type locality. The type locality of the species is traditionally accepted as “Transcaucasia”, according to the heading of the original publication: “Fauna entomologica Trans-Caucasica”. According to Breuning (1951), *Ph. (Musaria) puncticollis* was “Décrit par Faldermann sur des individus de Transcaucasie”. In fact, such definition is not quite adequate, as many new taxa, described by Faldermann (1937), are known from South Iran only.

The author accepted here the specimens from Azerbaijan (Talysh, Nakhichevan) and Armenia (Byurakan, Mt. Arailer, Khosrov, Megri) as representatives of the nominative subspecies. Three more subspecies were described. *Ph. (Musaria) p. stygia* Ganglbauer, 1884 was described from North Iran and is distributed in Turkmenistan, Kopetdag. *Ph. (Musaria) p. persica* Ganglbauer, 1884 was described from Persia on the base of the darker and robust specimens. The name was validated by Danilevsky (2020) for dark specimens from South Iran (Lorestan). *Ph. (Musaria) p. krupitskyi* Danilevsky, 2014 was described after a single totally black male from Eastern Turkey (Hakkâri).

A discovery of the species in Jordan was quite unexpected. A new subspecies is described below.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Material was collected manually. Specimens used in morphological studies were killed by ethyl acetate. All photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot

G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1-30.5 mm 1:2.8-4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

TAXONOMY

Phytoecia (Musaria) puncticollis vladyslavi Lazarev & Skrylnyk, **ssp. n.**

(Figs. 5, 10, 15, 20-21)

Type locality. Holotype, male, Jordan, 13 km WSW Mādabā, Qullat Umm Rusūm Mts., 31°39'47.13"N, 35°39'33.82"E, 662 m.

Description. Only one male available; body totally black, including antennae and legs; frons transverse, with very dense irregular conjugating punctation, with microdots among bigger punctures, with strong dense short black oblique setae; without interantennal depression, with a smooth shining spot between antennal tubercles; genae relatively wide, with fine punctation, wider than a half of lower eye lobe; occiput with moderately rough punctation; vertex slightly convex, with more regular punctation; eyes deeply emarginated, without connection between lower and upper eye lobes; the distance between lower and upper eye lobes behind antennal insertions about as wide as the base of scapus; antennae short, hardly reaching apical elytral fifth; 1st antennal joint short, about 1.1 times longer than 3rd joint, which is slightly thickened apically; other joints gradually diminishing in length.

Prothorax transverse, about 1.2 times shorter than basal width; angulately obtusely widened at middle; with moderately long black erect setae; pronotum slightly convex, with very dense rough punctation, with three wide shining callosities; scutellum transverse, semicircular.

Elytra about 2.5 times longer than basal width; with sides converging posteriorly, truncated apically; elytral punctation relatively big, moderately dense; short black oblique setae rather numerous near elytral bases, and indistinct at middle.

Abdomen with dense strong oblique black setae; pygidium and postpygidium slightly emarginated; last abdominal sternite rounded, with shallow apical depression.

Body length: 18.1 mm, body width: 5.5 mm.

Material. Holotype, male, Jordan, 13 km WSW Mādabā, Qullat Umm Rusūm Mts., 31°39'47.13"N, 35°39'33.82"E, 662 m, 29.3.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - collection of M. A. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia).

Differential diagnosis. The new taxon is characterized by totally black color, separated eye lobes, short 3rd antennal joint and rough elytral punctation. Black forms are not known in the nominative subspecies, besides the nominative subspecies has much longer antennae, with long 3rd joint, antennae nearly reach elytral apices in males and connected eye lobes. Totally black *Ph. (M.) p. stygia* also has long 3rd antennal joint and connected eye lobes. *Ph. (M.) p. persica* and *Ph. (M.) p. krupitskyi* have moderately long 3rd antennal joint; but eyes in *Ph. (M.) p. krupitskyi* have separated upper and lower eye lobes (connected in *Ph. (M.) p. persica*), besides *Ph. p. persica* has about a half of known specimens with red or partly red head.

Ph. (Musaria) wachanrui Mulsant, 1851 widely distributed in Palestine could be rather similar to *Ph. puncticollis* with about same color aberrations and also has black forms. But *Ph. wachanrui* is usually smaller (males up to 15 mm, females up to 18 mm), body relatively wider, scutellum white or yellowish. According to Plavilstshikov (1929), pale scutellum pubescence is very stable in *Ph. wachanrui* [*Ph. wachanrui* est une espèce très caractérisée par la pubescence blanche de l'écusson”].

Etymology. The new taxon is dedicated to Vladyslav Skrylnyk (Kharkiv, Ukraine) - the eldest son of the second author.

Figures 1-5. Male habitus, dorsal view. 1 - *Ph. (M.) p. puncticollis*: male, Armenia, Byurakan, 29.5.1982, M. Danilevsky; 2 - *Ph. (M.) p. stygia*: male, Turkmenistan, Kopet Dag Mts., Parkhai, 600 m, 16.4.1992, V. Grachev; 3 - *Ph. (M.) p. krupitskyi*: Holotype, male, Turkey, Hakkâri prov., Ağaçdibi, 37°30'02"N, 43°46'49"E, 1750 m, 1.6.2014, A. Krupitsky; 4 - *Ph. (M.) p. persica* Ganglbauer, 1884: male, Iran, Lorestan, 20 km S Ezna, 16-17.5.2017, S. Dementiev; 5 - *Ph. (M.) p. vladyslavi* **ssp. n.**: Holotype, male.

Figures 6-10. Anterior elytral punctuation. 6 - *Ph. (M.) p. puncticollis*: male, Azerbaijan, Talysh, Gasmalyan, 23.5.1987, A. Danchenko; 7 - *Ph. (M.) p. stygia*: male, Turkmenistan, Kopet Dag Mts., Parkhai. 16.4.1992, V.Grachev; 8 - *Ph. (M.) p. krupitskyi*: Holotype, male, Turkey, Hakkâri prov., Ağaçdibi, 37°30'02"N, 43°46'49"E, 1750 m, 1.6.2014, A. Krupitsky; 9 - *Ph. (M.) p. persica*: male, Iran, Lorestan, 20 km S Ezna. 33°16'46"N, 49°29'57"E, 2200 m, 16-17.5.2017, S. Dementiev; 10 - *Ph. (M.) p. vladyslavi* **ssp. n.**: Holotype, male.

Figures 11-15. Lower and upper eye lobes. 11 - *Ph. (M.) p. puncticollis*: male, Armenia, Megri, 15.6.1932; 12 - *Ph. (M.) p. stygia*: male, Turkmenistan, Kopet Dag Mts., Parkhai, 600 m, 16.4.1992, V. Grachev; 13 - *Ph. (M.) p. krupitskyi*: Holotype, male, Turkey, Hakkâri prov., Ağaçdibi, 37°30'02"N, 43°46'49"E, 1750 m, 1.6.2014, A. Krupitsky; 14 - *Ph. (M.) p. persica*: male, Iran, Lorestan, 20 km S Ezna. 33°16'46"N, 49°29'57"E, 2200 m, 16-17.5.2017, S. Dementiev; 15 - *Ph. (M.) p. vladyslavi* **ssp. n.**: Holotype, male.

Figures 16-20. 1st-5th male antennal joints. 16 - *Ph. (M.) p. puncticollis*: Armenia, Khosrov, 10-12.6.2003 1800-2500 m, 40°02'N, 45°02'E M.Danilevsky; 17 - *Ph. (M.) p. stygia*: Turkmenistan, Kopetdag Ridge, Parkhai, 600 m, 16.4.1992, V. Grachev; 18 - *Ph. (M.) p. krupitskyi*: Holotype, male, Turkey, Hakkâri prov., Ağaçdibi, 37°30'02"N, 43°46'49"E, 1750 m, 1.6.2014, A. Krupitsky; 19 - *Ph. (M.) p. persica*: Iran, Lorestan, 20 km S Ezna, 33°16'46"N, 49°29'57"E, 2200 m, 16-17.5.2017, S. Dementiev; 20 - *Ph. (M.) p. vladyslavi* **ssp. n.**: Holotype, male.

Figure 21. *Ph. (M.) p. vladyslavi* **ssp. n.**: Type locality.

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